

Lines (no.) and their reactions to bacterial leaf streak during 1973 and 1975 kharif, Pantnagar, India.

Reaction	Lines (no.) from		
	AICRIP		IRRI ^a
	1973	1975	
Resistant	5	32	38
Moderately resistant	10	22	22
Moderately susceptible	22	64	21
Susceptible	25	933	252
Highly susceptible	23	230	7
Total	85	1281	340

^aInternational Rice Observational Nursery.

RP 975-145-3-3, RP 572-9-2-1, RP 572-9-5-1, RP 633-367-1-2, RP 633-385-2-7, RP 2001-25-1, RP 2003-1-2-5, RP 2004-1-6-3, RP 2007- CRHP-1, R 32-2617, R 27-2546, RJR 107-305, 2-25 (upland paddy x BR 4-10), 24-7-3 (SR 3-9 x TN1), R 7-2-3-1, R 7-3-1-1, R 8-12-1-1, R 19-1-1-1, R 106-2-1-3-2, IR2071-557-6-4, IR2071-588-1-1-1, IR2071-875-2-3-4, IR2071-636-5-2-6, BR 3-12-B-15-40, BR 51-67-1/CI, BR 51-74-2, BR 44-11-1, BR 51-99-1, BR 51-243-1, BR 51-319-9, BR 52-8-1, B 459b-Pu-4-5-6-5, IR2031-238-4-2-2-3, IR2035-290-2-3-1, Purple check (15/IR1103-1), IR2070-210-3-3-4, IR2588-19-1-1, IR2681-34-5-6, IR2871-53-2, IR3264-13-158-2-935-3, IR3265-138-2-5, BG 11-11, Chianung-Seu Yu 8, SRR 6726-76-2-3, BIC-Md-3-3, IR2031-724-2-3-4, IR2071-636-5-5, IR2070-423-2-5-6, IR2035-290-2-1-3, IR2848-26-1, IR944-102-2-3-2, TN1, IR1539-823-1-4, IR26, IR5492-3-147 (Glb₂), IR1820-52-24-1, IR2070-24-1-4-5, and JPS.

Moderately resistant — CR 139-1058, RP 633-590-3-1-1-1, RP 632-94-1-2-1-1, RP 744-104-76-1, RP 744-104-76, UPR 4 D-25-2,45457 (TN1/Co 29) x Hansa, HPNS 32, TR 14, RP 633-308-1-2, RP 938-31-4-6, RP 2001-9-1, R 102-2609, R 106-2567, R 111-2583, R 32-2615, R 22-2522, 12-2 (TN1/BR4-10), 11-2 (TN1/BR 4-10), BR 1-2B-40-3, BR 43-1 1-2, BR 51-46-5, BR 51-49-6, 31-14 (upland paddy x BR 4-10), R 1-1-1-1, IR2070-414-3-9, BR 51-114-2, BR 51-331-4, Giza 172, B 1896-52-8-3-1,

B441b-126-2-3-1, IR1544-181-1-1, IR2035-255-2-3-1, IR2063-65-2-1, IR2063-152-3-2, IR2063-185-2-2, IR2070-834-1-2, IR2153-550-2-6, IR2786-120-1, IR2843-26-3, IR2071-625-1-252, IR2070-743-6-3-2, SPR 6726-134-2-26, IR1545-339-2-2, and RP 633-200-1-7-4-1.

Methods to artificially inoculate and screen rice varieties for resistance to stem rot disease under field conditions

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Two methods of inoculation for stem rot were tested during 1975–76: 1) placing a mycelial mass on potato-dextrose-agar among the injured culms of the hills, and 2) placing inoculum from autoclaved rice grains in the hills and tying the hills as in the International Rice Sheath Blight Nursery (IRSHBN). Ten hills each of 104 varieties were inoculated; at grain maturity, the inoculated hills were cut at the base for evaluation. The rotten tillers were counted by pressing between the fingers. Thirty-two varieties and lines showed less than 30% culm rotting and were rated as resistant. The rices that showed less than 20% culm infection included IR32, IR1529-680-3-2, IR2053-87-3-1, IR2061-214-3-3-28, IR2061-214-3-3-32,

Two methods of artificial inoculation for stem rot disease. Bangladesh Rice Research Institute.

Cultivar	Rotten tillers (%)		
	Mycelial mass	Grain inoculum	Av.
Chitraj	15	25	20
IR1817-2-143-3	20	25	23
IR944-85-1-2-1-1	21	23	22
IR910-12-3-1-1	9	36	23
BR9-17-6-4	12	29	21
BR13-231-1	25	31	28
IR579-80-1-2-1	27	31	29
IR20	25	38	32
IR781-177-3-2-2	28	39	34
Mukti	27	43	35
Kataktara	31	43	37
BR9-17-4-2	19	54	37
IR836-1-1-1	29	49	39
BR43-11-2	35	45	40
IR8	25	81	53
Chandina H/R 29-3	36	75	56

and Mahsuri (Improved). The IRSHBN method of placing grain inoculum was more effective than the other as shown by the higher percentage of infection in 16 varieties (see table).

Sources of resistance to ufra disease of rice in Bangladesh

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Eight species of wild rice and one cultivar were screened for resistance to ufra disease in the field and in pots. The wild rice species were *Oryza glaberrima*, *O. nivara*, *O. officinalis*, *O. perennis*, *O. rufipogon*, *O. sativa* var. *patua*, *O. spontanea*, and *O. subulata*. The *O. sativa* cultivar was R16-06. All plants were inoculated at the vegetative stage by introducing into the leaf sheath cavities about 1 ml of nematode suspension (approx. 1,000 *D. angustus*/ml) with a fine glass dropper. The inoculated potted plants were covered with polyethylene bags for 2 days to maintain proper humidity.

All the rices, except the wild species *O. subulata* and the cultivar R16-06, showed symptoms of ufra infection. *O. subulata* could not be infected at all. Although infection began on inoculated R16-06, the disease did not fully develop and no nematodes could be isolated from the plants at the mature stage. R16-06 is a deep-water rice that is sensitive to photoperiod, but its yield potential is low. *O. subulata* is a stiff-leaved rice. These two rices can be used as sources of resistance in future breeding programs for deep-water rice.

Rice disease survey: 1975

Summarized by H. E. Kauffman, joint coordinator and plant pathologist; T. Ebron, senior research assistant; and S. Merca, research assistant, International Rice Testing Program, IRRI

Scientists responded well to disease survey questionnaires sent out with the Rice Pathology Newsletter in late 1975. As in previous years, blast was the most widespread disease during 1975. It was